

Spot	Sequence
A01	IHGRFVMEDGSGSNT
A02	VMEDGSGSNTDLKQE
A03	SGSNTDLKQEVKTVN
A04	DLKQEVKTVNDETAS
A05	VKTVNDETASKSKER
A06	DETASKSKERTISTT
A07	KSKERT ISTTARN SK
A08	TISTTARN SKAASN
A09	ARN SKAASN GI SEK
A10	AASN GI SEK V KRLY
A11	GI SEK V KRLY GPTDM
A12	V KRLY GPTDM VK V FV
A13	G P TDM V K V F V P S IT
A14	V K V F V P S I T M F I V
A15	P V S I T M F I V T C V R N
A16	M F I V T C V R N F D I Y H
A17	T C V R N F D I Y H GV N L I
A18	F D I Y H GV N L I P T P Y V
A19	GV N L I P T P Y V I Y N E P
A20	P T P Y V I Y N E P A A D P G
A21	I Y N E P A A D P G T K L L H
A22	A A D P G T K L L H A V A N A
A23	T K L L H A V A N A A T F L V
A24	A V A N A A T F L V V A I S
A25	A T F L V V A I S T F A L L
A26	V V A I S T F A L L C L F Y
A27	T F A L L C L F Y K F Y C F
A28	C L F Y K F Y C F L T G F I

A29	KFYCFLTGFIMFSTF
A30	LTGFIMFSTFLLVSL
B01	MFSTFLLVSLFSFVQ
B02	LLVSL FSFVQYQQIL
B03	FSFVQYQQIL SDLNV
B04	YQQILSDLNVPVSI
B05	SDLNVPVSI
B06	PVSIVFIGFLHINLS
B07	FIGFLHINLSAIELM
B08	HINLSAIELM SIFW K
B09	AIELM SIFW K GP MRL
B10	SIFW K GP MRL Q QASL
B11	GP MRL Q QASL I LIAV
B12	Q QASL I LIAV T TLT
B13	I L IAV T TLT I M Q IL
B14	T TLT I M Q IL P Q W T S
B15	I M Q I L P Q W T S W A L L V
B16	P Q W T S W A L L V T L A L W
B17	W A L L V T L A L W D L F A V
B18	T L A L W D L F A V L T P C G
B19	D L F A V L T P C G P L L
B20	L T P C G P L L L V E T A E
B21	P L K L L V E T A E R E R G E D
B22	V E T A E R E R G E D L M P A I
B23	E R G E D L M P A I I Y T G S
B24	L M P A I I Y T G S A S L P Q
B25	I Y T G S A S L P Q S D S I E
B26	A S L P Q S D S I E S R R T S
B27	S D S I E S R R T S E V K E C
B28	S R R T S E V K E C T P V Q D

B29	EVKECTPVQDKVKS
B30	TPVQDKVKSVPSSGR
C01	KVKS V P S S G R F I E S F
C02	P S S G R F I E S F R M P S L
C03	F I E S F R M P S L K S N D D
C04	R M P S L K S N D D E R N I R
C05	K S N D D E R N I R L G L G D
C06	E R N I R L G L G D F I F Y S
C07	L G L G D F I F Y S L L V G T
C08	F I F Y S L L V G T A S T H G
C09	L L V G T A S T H G D W A T T
C10	A S T H G D W A T T L A L F R
C11	D W A T T L A L F R V Y L N R
C12	L A L F R V Y L N R S W F H S
C13	V Y L N R S W F H S C S P S
C14	S W F H S C S P S T S K G T
C15	C S P S T S K G T A S T T N
C16	T S K G T A S T T N I R H I W
C17	A S T T N I R H I W C D R Y F
C18	I R H I W C D R Y F S S R F A
C19	C D R Y F S S R F A M S K F A
C20	S S R F A M S K F A V E L N R
C21	M S K F A V E L N R K Q I F I
C22	
C23	D R E K L Q E R L A K L A G
C24	H P G S V N E F D F
C25	A V N F P N P P G K G G
C26	Q E V R K Y F

Entry	E-value	Score	Ident (%)	Organism	Protein name	Length
C7BVX5	-	-	-	<i>Angiostrongylus cantonensis</i>	Presenilin	415
A0A0K0DB71	0.0	1,584	77.5	<i>Angiostrongylus cantonensis</i>	Presenilin	414
A0A0D8XWV7	1.3e-132	1,005	64.2	<i>Dictyocaulus viviparus</i>	Presenilin	315
A0A016U204	5.4e-110	866	45.7	<i>Ancylostoma ceylanicum</i>	Presenilin	425
A0A016TZZ8	9.6e-108	852	45.6	<i>Ancylostoma ceylanicum</i>	Presenilin	435
A0A0R3PEK8	1.0e-128	972	79.8	<i>Angiostrongylus costaricensis</i>	Presenilin	409
G0N7M3	6.5e-118	904	77.0	<i>Caenorhabditis brenneri</i>	Presenilin	444

A

B

1: -----IHGRFVMEGSGSNTDLKQEVKTVNDTASKSKERTI-----STTARNskaASTNGISEKVKRLYGPTDMVKVF 69
 2: ----- 0
 3: -----MEDGSGSNTDLKQEVKTVNDTASKSKERTI-----STTARNskaASTNGISEKVKRLYGPTDMVKVF 63
 4: MSSSTVCTEQELVLSGIDTSEE--SP-ITMANEARSRSGNENVNGSRPTTSAEVATTSAEIASSSRKEKNYGPQDMVKVF 77
 5: MS-SSKSIGKTLVYKIDARHD--EE-DAITGEKKRRGENAAAAGSS-----RAKAKKSTSHRQHEKNYGPQDMVKVF 69
 6: --P-----SCTS-----QPGTQEHPA-----TVRRTSTLGSGENEEEEAEELKYGASHVINLF 45
 7: MPY-----SREP-----QDGGGNTSASSETHTT---YGTNLISNRSEPEEENQVEEAELKYGASHVIHLF 57

	PSAg1	PSAg2	PSAg3	
1:	VPVSITMFIVVTCVRNFDIYHGVNLIPTPYVIYNEPAADPGTKLLHAVANAATFLVVAISTFALLCLFYKFCFLTGF			149
2:	-----MIYTEPDDAVTELLHAINASTFLLLVISTFLLFLFYKFCYLLHGF			50
3:	VPVSITMFIVVTCVRNFDIYHGVNLIPTPYVIYNEPAADPGTKLLHAVANAATFLVVAISTFLLCLFYKFCYCTG---			140
4:	VPVICMAIVTVITRTVEIYRQDVTIKTPYVIYHDPEAEAPTCLWHSLVNAATFLCVIVVSTFGVLALFYKFCYRCLNF			157
5:	VPVICMTIIVICTRNVEVYQKDIILRTPYVIYHDPEAETPTKLWHSVMNAVLLCVVVVATFGVLALFYKFCYRCLNF			149
6:	VPVICMVMVFTMNTVTFYSYNDGRHLLYTPFKETDSTSEKVLMSLGNALVMLCVIIMTVILIVFYKYRCYKVIW			125
7:	VPVSLCMALVFTMNTITFYSQNGRHLLYTPFKETDSIVEKGLMSLGNALVMLSVVIVMTVLLIFFYKYKFKYKLIHGW			137

	PSAg4	PSAg5	
1:	IMFSTFLLVSLFSFVQYQIILSDLNVP-----VSIVFIGFLHINLSAIELMSIFWKGPMLRQASLILIAVTV		217
2:	IMLSTFMLVTLFSFMQYQIILSDLNIP-----VSIVVMVFIHLNIAVVQLMSIFWIGPMKVQGSILISVTV		118
3:	-----YFRQIILSDLNVP-----VSIVFIGFLHINLAAIELMSIFWKGPMLRQASLILIAVTV		193
4:	IMFSTFMLITTAASLMQYEVLRAINFP-----ISSATVLLLHTNMAVIGLMSIFWKGPMLRQASLILIAVTV		225
5:	FMFATFMLITIMTALQYHEILRAINVP-----VSAVTFLLHLNVAVIGLMSIFWKGPMLRQASLILIAVTV		217
6:	LMVSSCLLLFLFSTIYFAVL--KSFTSCEFSFFQRSDEKAVETTASMFSLRFFLLLDSTCLTHCH--PFFQFYLIAMSALM		202
7:	LISSFLLLFLFTAIYVQEVLSKFDVS-----PSVILVLFGLGNYGVLGMMCIHWKGPLRLQFYLIITMSALM		205

	PSAg6	PSAg7	
1:	TLTIMQILPQWTSWALLVTLALWDLFAVLTPCGPLKLLVETAERGEDLMPAIYTGASLPSQDSI-----		284
2:	TLTIMQILPKWTSWTLVTLALWDLFAVLSPCGPLKLLVETAERGEDLMPAMIYTGIAFLQSTSSK-----		186
3:	TLTIMQILPQWTSWALLVTLALWDLFAVLTPCGPLKLLVETAERGEDLMPAIYSMLVLLHFNQTLNVARQKLN--		272
4:	TLTIMRVLPRTWNWAMVILLAFWDLCAVLSPCGPKILVETAERGEDLMPAIYTGAAASIEKTESTQ-----		293
5:	TLTIMRVFPKWTSWAIVILLAFWDIFAVLSPCGPLKILVEIAEERDEELMAAIYSTQPFEEKKLLTYDI---CIS-A		293
6:	ALVFIKYLPEWTVWVSLAVISVWDLIAVLAPNGPLRILVETAERNEPIFPALIYSS--GIIPYVLTAVKNSEEGTEMP		281
7:	ALVFIKYLPEWTVWVFLVVISVWDLVAVLTPKGPLRILVETAERNEPIFPALIYSS--GIIPYVLTAVKNSEEGTEMP		384

	PSAg8	
1:	-----ESRRTSEVKECTPVQDK----VKSVPs-----SGRFIESFRMPS-----LKS-NDDERNIRLGLGD	335
2:	-----SPTSAEVEGSSPIKDK----IKT-KS-----SGNTVESLRMPS-----LNS-EAEERNIRLGLGD	235
3:	GIEIFDDGKPAISYKFIVPRDCTPVQDK----VKSVPs-----SGRFIESFRMPS-----LKS-NDDERNIRLGLGD	334
4:	G----SQTPP-----TAVDRSPTNEK----RSASRS-----PLRRSGSQPIPS-----NSVSAEESNIRLGLGD	345
5:	GSATLSRTEPKQSDLSASGEESPTK-E----RRSSRS-----SVRTVESLRIPS-----FSETDEEDRNIRLGLGD	355
6:	IS-----SNLPLE-----FVFS-CFEACFTAGMVPsFLVLHN-----VVQICNISEGVKLGLED	329
7:	TTSSASSSQPSNVPKTKTKVKRIPQKQVQIETNVSSNPQGETPVARVERERQPIVNVPEVQYVRHEDYQEEKGVKLGLED	364

	PSAg9	PSAg10	PSAg11	PSAg12	PSAg13	
1:	FIFYSLLVGTASTHGDWATTLALFRVYLNRSWFHSCSPSSTSGKTASTTNIRHIWCDRYFSSRFAMSKFAVELNRKQIFI					415
2:	FIFYSLLVGSASVDGDWTTLACFVSILTGLGFTLVLLVILQKALPALPISITFGVLAYFSSRYAVSKFVLELNRLMFL					315
3:	FIFYSLLVGTASTHGDWATTLACFVSILTGLGFTLVLLVILQKALPALPISVTFGVIAFSSRFAMSKFAVELNRKQIFI					414
4:	FIFYSLLVGNATVLADWTTIVACAVSILVGLAFTLVLLVIFQKALPALPISIAFGAIAFFSSKFVTSKYLDRLNSEQIFI					425
5:	FIFYSILVGNAAVLADLTTILACFVSILVGLGFTLVLLVIFQKALPALPISIAFGAIAFFVSKLVTSKLIDQLNKEAIFL					435
6:	FIFYSVLVGKASSYFDWNTTVACYVAIVLGLCFTLVLLAVFRRALPALPISIFAGLLFYFCTRWIVTPYVSEITRRQWVY					409
7:	FIFYSVLLGKASSYFDWNTTACVVAIVLGLCFTLVLLAVFRRALPALPISIFAGLLFYFCTRWIITPFVTKFTQNCLLY					444